

Complexities in Ubiquitous Computing Environments of Software Ecosystems

Elia Salerno , elia.salerno@zhdk.ch

BA Interaction Design Student Zurich University of the Arts

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Abstract

In the rapidly evolving landscape of technology, the integration of ubiquitous computing into big-scale service design has become a transformative force, reshaping user experiences within software ecosystems. This paper delves into the dynamic interplay between technological ecosystems, service design principles, and the evolving user journey created by the opaque information architecture of Software Ecosystems. Drawing insights from case studies, and contemporary trends, the paper explores the advantages, limitations, and user choices and alternatives in the era of ubiquitous computing.

Keywords: Technological Ecosystems, Ubiquitous Computing, Service Design, User Experience Design, Internet of Things

1.1 Software ecosystems (SECOs)

A Software Ecosystem, or in short SECO is a rapidly evolving phenomenon in the software engineering field, describing the dynamics among companies in the software industry as they develop and integrate ubiquitous services and interfaces (Barbosa & Alves, 2011). This collaborative approach among various entities creates interesting partnerships, encouraging organizations to consider not only internal operations but also dynamics with external entities, ultimately benefiting end-users.

A concise example of a SECO is the Apple ecosystem. In this ecosystem, various software applications, services and devices seamlessly integrate and interact, creating a unified (ubiquitous) experience for users. For instance, Apple devices like iPhones, iPads, Macs, and Apple Watches work together with software such as iOS, macOS, and apps like iCloud, creating a cohesive environment for users to sync data, access content, and enjoy a consistent user experience across different devices and platforms. You can lay out a SECO with a „Service Blueprint“, to get an overview how interconnected the different layers which are visible and invisible to the user really are (Kuniavsky, 2010).

Inspired by properties observed in natural and business ecosystems, SECOs encapsulate both technical and business dimensions of software development, leading to both desired and undesired partnerships between companies. Historically, collaborations for outsourcing software technology to other companies have been common (Barbosa & Alves, 2011). However, a contemporary shift is notable, with major companies such as Google, Apple, Meta, Microsoft, Samsung, Netflix, and others (Peters, 2023) taking the lead in constructing comprehensive SECOs. These industry giants are now building various features and software packages into their systems, aiming to gain a competitive advantage. A good example

would be Netflix, which set up Netflix Games seemingly out of the blue in 2021 to „keep subscribers engaged in between seasons of their favorite shows“ (Richardson, 2023).

This shift reflects a paradigm where every technology company seeks to establish and control their own ecosystem as much as possible and make them appeal to all kinds of customers. The emergence of SECOs thus signifies a transformative trend in software development, emphasizing collaborative and interconnected processes to shape the future of the industry.

1.2 Types of Software Ecosystems (SECOs)

SECOs, come in various forms, and their differences are quite noticeable. One way to classify them is by using the terms closed and open SECOs, each having its own advantages and disadvantages.

Closed SECOs are typically governed by one or a multiple entities that collaborate with each other. These ecosystems excel in seamless integration with proprietary tools, delivering a standardised and cohesive user experience. However, the trade-off lies in limited third-party integration opportunities and closed-source code, restricting user modifications and fostering potential data privacy implications. An example that will later on be discussed more in depth is Apple's iOS.

On the flip side, open SECOs are either governed by an organisation (mostly NGO's) or a community. Their main stand-out are third-party implementations, with which they foster collaboration and innovation. This also creates discourse in community settings and forums. These ecosystems often prioritise customisability and compatibility, sometimes at the cost of stability. Notably, open SECOs are character-

ised by the availability of open-source code, promoting transparency and the collective improvement of software through community contributions. An example that will be discussed more in depth later on is Linux.

Interestingly, some ecosystems blur the lines between openness and closure, embodying a hybrid model of both closed and open. This allows for an approach, which capitalises on the strengths of both paradigms to create a versatile and adaptable environment. An example that could be drawn here is Microsoft's Windows.

The choice between open and closed ecosystems is of course subjective and depends on user preferences and needs.

1.3 Ubiquitous Computing and the Internet of Things (IoT)

In today's landscape of smart watches, voice assistants and all kinds of other smart devices, ubiquitous computing and the internet of things have both become realities in some form. From a UX designer's perspective, having multiple devices working together flawlessly is quite the task.

„When designing one part of a larger system, understanding how that part works and defining its role within the larger system is important and often inspirational for designers. Task flows are a good way of visually understanding this type of information.“ (Kolko, 2011, p. 116)

Doing this in a closed ecosystem can be quite challenging already, but now thinking of an open ecosystem, it is completely another story. Not only do you have to keep in mind all the different scenarios, you have to also think of

different technical limitations and bottlenecks to consider in your design, to have an optimal experience on a variety of devices.

1.4 Smart Devices and Services

What is also currently pushing the IoT in smart devices is the notion of streaming. You don't have to own a song, movie or book anymore to access it, you just need to stream it. This of course involves risks but it comes with great potentials, which are already greatly being used and improve the ubiquitous computing experience and comfort a lot. Not having to store or run most of the heavy lifting on a smart device, gives the manufacturers the opportunity to turn small, low-end and cost effective technology into IoT devices and thus having even more gadgets and helpers connected with each other and the web.

As the trend continues to gain momentum, it reshapes the way people consume and interact with digital content, creating a dynamic landscape for innovation and user engagement in the digital ecosystem.

2.1 Closed Software Ecosystems

A really good reference example of a closed ecosystem is Apple's iOS, since it is really built out and thus covers a lot of different gadgets and services, but similar case studies can also be taken from the likes of Alphabet (Google), Meta (Facebook), Microsoft or even Super Apps like Tencent's WeChat and so on. Taking the example of Apple though, you got iOS and MacOS, which tightly work together with many services like the Apple ID, the Keychain, AirDrop, Handoff and the iCloud (drive), which is the only natively supported backup solution for iOS devices. This list goes on and on, but what you quickly will find out is that if you use a non-apple device with other apple devices, that many of these functionalities fall away. For

example syncing photos from a iOS to a Windows device or any other case, it just becomes a big hassle since you need to find workarounds or if you are lucky supported, well working 3rd party applications that deliver the functionality you need, which have always been rare to find on the Apple App Store and since there is no side loading allowed on iOS this is your only bet. Also the other way around, if you are subscribed to one of the Apple Services, like Apple TV, you will quickly find that there is no App on the Android Playstore for it. On the other hand, if you are working with Apple device only, everything seems to work flawlessly with each other and the User Experience is vastly different from mixing devices and services (Kuniavsky, 2010).

2.2 Magical moments

Going on with the Apple case study, there is a lot of little experiences, especially in multi-scale user experience design, that work just incredibly good, in fact so good that you don't notice them anymore and they seem to blend in with everything you always do on a day-to-day basis (Kuniavsky, 2010). You go on a commute, pick up your iPhone, start up Apple Music, your AirPods automatically connect when opened, you start working on your MacBook Pro and the music can be controlled from both points, you get a call and are able to pick it up from your MacBook, then you need to transfer a document to your phone which is easily done with AirDrop, after your internet research on your MacBook you close it and can just continue with the same page opened in Safari on your iPhone and so on. This little flow could be extended with so many Apple devices and Services but you get the point. I call these experiences that just seamlessly work „Magical moments“, because they really do emit the feeling of magic. Designing not only for a single device at once but instead for a full line of

devices and services is a really tricky thing to do, because there are just so many variables to the equation. Since Apple's Ecosystem is closed though and thus Apple has full control over every endpoint in the service design, they are able to deliver state of the art user experience over their entire SECO. This cannot be found anywhere else, at least not to this extent, which is why it has always been a big draw in factor for people to buy into the Apple Ecosystem and since the features are just this convenient, practical and natural to use, they will always be able to attract people into buying more of their devices and services, even if it is at the cost of giving all your data to a single company.

3.1 Open Software Ecosystems

A notable example of an open ecosystem is exemplified by the Linux operating system, with its remarkable compatibility across a diverse range of devices. In contrast to closed ecosystems, Linux, embraces a wide array of third-party implementations and modifications. This includes the ability to sideload apps and attain full root access for personalized customization. The extensive suite of software associated with Linux caters to a multitude of needs and it is especially well regarded in the software development, machine learning and data science communities, due to its robust kernel and strong support of these communities.

Furthermore, the Linux operating system stands out for its open-source code, facilitating collaborative development and diverse approaches to shaping the Linux system. This openness extends beyond companies to include third parties and communities, allowing them to craft their unique „flavors“ of the Linux system, which resulted in an uncountable amount of so-called Linux distributions.

Nevertheless, the openness of the Linux ecosystem comes with its set of challenges. While the flexibility is advantageous, it may give rise to incompatibility issues between different distros, specific software or hardware.

Another open software ecosystem would be Google's Android. While it is not governed by an NGO, you can still apply basically all the same things said about Linux, since it is also open source and there is a big community supporting it.

3.2 Technological freedom

Unlike the Magical Moments, which await you in Apple's Ecosystem, you are mostly responsible to create a framework that includes all the necessary tools you need and works together. Sure there are already many pre-installed Google features that deliver Magical UX Moments, but they don't work in every (device combination) scenario and often need some workaround to be working seamlessly. But if you are willing to handle extra bugfixing, setting up, reading documentation and playing around, you really get access to an open world of apps, plugins, ad-ons and other functionality. The community is there to help you.

4.1 Hacking

People have long been crowning ecosystems as being unrivaled, though people have also been trying to hack their ecosystem of choice to their needs. This can be observed inside of both closed and open SECOs.

Within the closed ecosystems, with the likes of iOS, the Kindle or even Console Operating systems like Sony's Playstation, there have always been notions of so-called Jailbreaks, most famous being the iOS Jailbreak, which is a process that removes software restrictions im-

sed by Apple on its devices, allowing users to access and modify the core system files. This enables the installation of unauthorized apps, customizations, and tweaks not approved by Apple, potentially compromising the device's security and stability.

On the other hand within open ecosystems, people try to modify applications, ad-ons, the operating system and even Bootloader itself to get the most reliable and customized experience.

4.2 Conclusion and lookout

Looking ahead, the way we use technology is changing, and the future will be shaped by how software ecosystems develop and adapt to new trends. Big companies like Google, Apple, Meta, and Microsoft are not just making software; they're building entire ecosystems.

We can see that there are two main types of ecosystems. Closed ones, like Apple's iOS, provide smooth, controlled and partly restrictive experiences and open ecosystems, like Linux or Google's Android give users more freedom and options to customize and explore a wide range of apps and features. It is really hard to define an ecosystem to be either closed or open, since there is not a set of rules to clearly define them, only made up guidelines and ideas, which also means that many of the existing SECO's, like Microsoft's Windows, are something in between.

In the ever-evolving tech worlds, the infusion of ubiquitous computing into extensive service design has created a really noticeable shift in user experiences within software ecosystems. It really shows how far UX and Interaction Design have come by shifting the devices and systems, previously only technology enthusiasts were able to make use of to entire SECO's

pretty much every person worldwide is able to navigate, at least to some degree. They were able to do this, by creating „Magical Moments“, which makes users enjoy even more complicated tasks on a day to day basis, even if it is at the cost of customization.

While some ecosystems prioritize user flexibility, allowing extensive customization, others prioritize simplicity and a user-friendly experience. I personally love mixing and matching different systems, devices and services with each other and getting things to work for my specific need. For doing this, I never shy away of extra efforts and playing around. Since I use such a wide variety of devices, I don't prefer closed or open ecosystems over the other since it really depends on the usecases and current needs.

In essence, the persistent tension between closed and open ecosystems persists, each offering unique advantages and challenges. As software ecosystems continue to evolve, the dynamic interplay between technological ecosystems, service design, and user experiences will play an important role in shaping the future of software development, user engagement and user experience.

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